

Conflict Management Styles of Principals in Selected Campuses of a Private Educational System

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14189879

Maria Rona Rhia Escalo Halaman

Saint Francis of Assisi College

Abstract

A principal's conflict management strategies are indispensable in the attainment of the school's goals and objectives. Accordingly, this study was conducted to determine the conflict management styles used by principals in selected campuses of a private educational system which were assessed by 129 teacher-respondents using the adapted ROCI-II Form B. Majority of the teacher-respondents are 20-30 years old, college graduate, have rendered less than 5 years in the institution, and without administrative load. Individual causes of conflicts were the most common conflicts experienced in the system. Regardless of age, educational attainment, or workload, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the principal's conflict management styles showed that the principals often used the different styles with Collaborating as the most used conflict management style. Results of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of the Competing and Compromising style when grouped according to age. Also, irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the different conflict management styles. However, the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of conflict management styles vary when grouped according to educational attainment and length of service. Though different conflict management styles were generally assessed as often used by principals, there is still a high frequency of occurrence of individual and managerial causes of conflicts experienced by both teachers and principals. To address this, a program for the enhancement of relevant skills in conflict management to manage conflicts at different levels or situations was submitted as an output of this study.

Keywords: *Conflict management, enhancement program, principals*

Introduction

School principals today are challenged with more complex pressures, changes, and aggression; and consequently, countless conflicts with which to cope. Different factors contribute to the conflict. Principals are fortunate to have at their disposal an increasing amount of literature that treats matters of conflict in a meaningful way. In the face of this vast amount of literature, a study made by Msila (2012) asserted that only a few principals are adequately trained to manage conflict. They frequently misunderstand the role of conflict and believe that it should be avoided or stopped promptly.

Kenneth W. Thomas defines conflict as "the condition in which people's concerns (the things they care about) appear to be incompatible" (Eklund, 2010). Conflict is an inevitable component of any workplace. However, when it occurs and is not handled effectively, there is a propensity for morale to suffer, absenteeism to rise, and productivity to fall. According to The University of Oklahoma Human Resources (2019), managers spend at least 25% of their time managing workplace disagreements, resulting in lower office performance.

The interactionist school of thinking on conflict claims that conflict may be both productive and harmful since it stimulates self-criticism, innovation, and essential transformation (Robbins, Judge, & Campbell, 2010). A conflict had been perceived to be bad and negative, and thus should be disregarded or eliminated. However, a disagreement can be useful if it is leveraged to effect change or innovation. Conflict can strengthen an organization's decision-making and employee relations. While conflict serves to be beneficial, it still wastes the organization's resources and energy. Consequently, conflict management is one of the most essential skills for managers. Rahim (as cited by Manila, 2016) stated that the aim of conflict management is to enhance learning and group outcomes, including effectiveness or performance in an organizational setting. In dealing with conflict, the critical issue is not so much on the conflict itself but on how it is managed.

Conflicts in the country's public schools have been on the rise in recent years, according to the Department of Education (as cited by Cerado, 2013). This is primarily because of unsolved disagreements among students, instructors, and school administrators. These have had a negative impact on the school's and pupils' academic achievement. Thus, school administrators' understanding of conflict resolution is seen to improve learning, thereby enhancing students' academic performance. Furthermore, Edet, Benson, and Williams (2017) argued that characteristics such as the principal's leadership styles, change management methods, and conflict resolution strategies may be possible sources of conflict and may have a major impact on teachers' job effectiveness. This implies that principals must have the necessary abilities and approaches to handle conflicts in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the educational curriculum in schools.

According to the preceding, the school as a social institution has its own norms and values, and it is distinguished by complex connections among its members: principals, teachers, non-teaching staff, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Conflicts do emerge among members of the school system due to the high degree of interdependence of duties and individual variances in job expectations, and would be resolved through

the different conflict management approaches. The researcher decided to perform this investigation based on these premises.

Conflict resolution tactics employed by a principal are critical to the achievement of the school's goals and objectives. If a principal is not knowledgeable about conflict resolution, it will have a detrimental impact on the performance of teachers and pupils; however, if a conflict is managed constructively, it will improve organizational performance (Uchendu, Anijao bi-idem, & Odigwe, 2013). Accordingly, this study aimed to determine the conflict management styles used by principals in selected campuses of a private educational system.

The results of this study became a basis for the enhancement of management development programs, specifically, a series of training for the principals to be adept of the different styles of conflict management and develop the relevant skills and to manage conflicts at different levels or situations with a view of carrying out the school's vision, mission, goals, and objectives and to provide guidance on how administrators should manage conflicts, especially in their respective schools.

This study was grounded on Rahim's Five Styles of Conflict Management (as cited in Kassim, Manaf, Abdullah, Osman, & Salahudin, 2018), a two-dimensional framework. In a conflict situation, the first dimension is the degree to which a person satisfies his concerns; the second dimension is the degree to which a person satisfies the concerns of the other. Combining these two variables yields five conflict resolution styles: integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising. Each of us, according to (Thomas & Killmann, 2015), is capable of using all five conflict management approaches. There is no such thing as a singular style of coping with conflict. However, some persons employ particular models better than others and, as a result, rely on those modes more heavily than others, whether due to temperament or practice.

Figure 1. Model Concept of the Moderating Role of Work Mattering Between Job Satisfaction and Life Satisfaction

Figure 1 represents the model concept of the study which shows the two types of conflict: the functional and dysfunctional conflict. Functional conflicts are also constructive conflicts that can be channeled into discovering positive solutions that meet people's needs, as well as motivating teams to look at a problem that might otherwise go unnoticed. These confrontations generate fresh ideas for existing problems, as well as greater enthusiasm and renewed energy to solve a specific problem. Dysfunctional conflicts are negative disputes that do not contribute to team cohesion and trust; do not move toward consensus solutions; diminish efficiency; produce unpleasant feelings between parties; cause disruption; and divert team energy to a disadvantageous path. The figure further shows that conflicts are essential; it is the management that sets the difference –if managed well, the result is functional conflict. If mismanaged, the consequences are dysfunctional conflict. Also, it is through intensified series of training that conflict management skills can be enhanced.

Methods

Research Design

This study is a quantitative type of research that used descriptive design since the researcher described the conflict management style of the school principals of a private educational system. Amorado, Boholano, and Talili (2017) defined descriptive research as a study that describes what exists and may help to uncover new facts and meaning.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 129 Preschool to Senior High School teachers from the big campuses of SFAC (Bacoar, Las Piñas, Taguig). Majority (80 or 62.02%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the 20-30 age group; 21 (26.28%) belong to 41-50; 15 (11.62%) belong to 51-60; 13 (10.08%) belong to the 31-40 age

group. In terms of highest educational attainment, the majority (105 or 81.40%) of the teacher respondents are college graduates; 19 (14.73%) are with Master's Units; 4 (3.10%) are Master's Graduate, and 1 (0.77%) has Doctorate Units. Further, in terms of length of service, majority (86 or 66.67%) of the teacher-respondents belong to the 5 years and below bracket; 20 (15.50%) rendered 21 or more years serving the institution; 12 (9.30%) rendered 16-20 years; 6 (4.65%) rendered 11-15 years, and 5 (3.88%) rendered 6-10 years serving the institution. There are more teacher-respondents (96 or 74.42%) without administrative load than that of the teacher-respondents (33 or 25.58%) with an administrative load. The three principals of the abovementioned campuses were also surveyed and interviewed on the conflicts they encounter in school and on the conflict management styles they use in resolving conflicts.

Instrumentation

The researcher adapted the Rahim Organizational Conflict Inventory II (ROCI-II Form B) of Dr. Azfal Rahim. The researcher modified the questionnaire by adding a checklist to it and transforming it into three parts. The first part is the (I) Checklist which contains the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service in school. The second part (II) is another checklist of the different conflicts experienced by the respondents inside the school which will be rated according to its frequency of occurrence which used the following scale:

Option	Description	Statistical Limit
4	Very High	3.50 – 4.00
3	High	2.50 – 3.49
2	Low	1.50 – 2.59
1	Very Low	1.00 – 1.49

A higher score means the more frequent the occurrence.

The last part is the (III) 28-item Questionnaire which is designed to measure five independent dimensions of conflict management styles: Collaborating (CB), Accommodating (AC), Competing (CM), Avoiding (AV), and Compromising (CO). The questionnaire was also modified by replacing the (pronoun) word "I" with "He" at the beginning of every item and changing the arbitrary scale used to describe the result with:

Option	Description	Statistical Limit
4	Always (A)	3.50 – 4.00
3	Often (O)	2.50 – 3.49
2	Seldom (Se)	1.50 – 2.59
1	Never (N)	1.00 – 1.49

The styles of handling conflict were measured by 7, 6, 5, 6, and 4 statements respectively, selected based on repeated factor and item analysis. A higher score represents a greater use of a conflict management style.

On the other hand, to know the perspective of the principals regarding their conflict management style, another questionnaire and interview questions were prepared. The questionnaire contained two parts. The first part is the (I) Checklist which contains the profile of the principal in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of as a school principal/OIC principal. The second part (II) is the (III) 28-item Questionnaire which is designed to measure five independent dimensions of conflict management styles: Collaborating (CB), Accommodating (AC), Competing (CM), Avoiding (AV), and Compromising (CO).

The questionnaire was presented to the thesis adviser for checking and validation.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought the approval of the SFAC President thru the managing director for using the name of the school in the research study and for the distribution of the questionnaire to the selected campuses.

Upon approval, the researcher then sent letters to the principal of the selected campuses to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents after one of their general meetings to ensure immediate retrieval of the questionnaires and its confidentiality and to have a short interview with them at their most convenient time.

Data gathered were tallied by the researcher using a frequency distribution table. Data tallied were then analyzed, interpreted, and presented with the help of a statistician.

Results and Discussion

Table 1
Assessment on Conflicts Experienced by the Teacher-respondents

No.	Criteria	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
1	Individual Causes	2.75	High	1
2	Managerial Causes		2.51 High	2
3	Other Causes (depending on the organizational culture)		2.46 Low	3
Overall Mean			2.53 High	

Legend: Very High 3.50-4.00; High 2.50-3.49; Low 1.50-2.49; Very Low 1.00-1.49

Table 1 shows the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflicts experienced by them. Individual causes with a mean of 2.75 the interpretation of "High" ranked number 1. The result was also proven in the study conducted by Sumera-Icutan and Sumera-Sagaoinit (2017) that interpersonal conflicts appeared to be the most prevalent type of conflict. Moreover, the managerial causes with a mean of 2.51 were also interpreted as "High" and ranked 2nd. However, other identified causes of conflict, with a mean of 2.46, were interpreted as "Low" and ranked 3rd. The data also implies that other causes (depending on the organizational culture) of conflict were least important, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, compared to the individual and managerial causes, respectively.

Generally, the overall assessment of the teacher-respondents on conflicts experienced by them is "High" based on the overall mean of 2.53 and, while workplace conflict is inescapable, it is thought to be beneficial in the building of high-performing organizations (McNamara, 2013).

Table 2
Overall Assessment of the Teacher-respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by Principals

Conflict Management Style	Mean	Interpretation	Ranking
Collaborating		3.12 Often	1
Accommodating	2.94	Often	2
Competing		2.62 Often	4
Avoiding	2.53	Often	5
Compromising		2.87 Often	3
Overall Mean		2.82 Often	

Legend: Always 3.50-4.00; Often 2.50-3.49; Seldom 1.50-2.49; Never 1.00-1.49

Table 2 presents the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflict management styles used by principals. Collaboration received the highest mean of 3.12 and the interpretation of "Frequently." This indicates that principals should involve and collaborate with their subordinates in dealing with issues in their schools. Being ranked one suggests that Collaborating is the most commonly employed conflict management approach among the principals. In his study, Ladeo (as referenced by Manila, 2016) discovered that most administrators regarded integrating as one of the most substantial and highly desirable strategies in conflict management. Furthermore, the result agrees with the answers of the principals. Their responses under Collaborating got an overall mean of 4.00 with a verbal interpretation of "Always". Other than that, when asked: "How often do you use the collaborating style?" the principals answered "Always".

This was followed by Accommodating with a mean of 2.83. This demonstrates that while dealing with problems, principals frequently aim to meet the expectations of their instructors, giving in to their proposals and viewpoints. This technique, according to Friedman, Tidd, Currall, and Tsai (as referenced by Manila, 2016), provides a simple way to resolve conflicts. One party just gives in to the other party, reducing friction. Being rank 2, this also suggests that Accommodating is the second most-used conflict resolution style of the principals. The result agrees with the responses of the principals when their responses under Accommodating got an overall mean of 2.89 and the interpretation of "Often" ranked number 2. Moreover, when asked: "How often do you use the collaborating style?" the principals answered "Sometimes", "Oftentimes", and "Sometimes".

Compromising ranked 3rd with a mean of 2.87 and the interpretation of "Often". This demonstrates that while dealing with problems, the principals frequently choose the middle ground by utilizing give and take circumstances. According to Rahim (2012), the majority of managers used a compromising strategy to address complicated problems and devise successful solutions. Furthermore, the result aligns with the responses of the principals when they assessed Compromising as their 3rd most-used conflict management style with an overall mean of 2.42 and the interpretation of "Seldom".

Competing ranked 4th with a mean of 2.62 and the interpretation of "Often". This demonstrates that, when compared to other conflict management approaches, the dominant style was employed less by school administrators in addressing disagreements in their schools. It is consistent with the findings of Ghaffar et al. (2012) discovered that instructors believed that principals frequently or never used a domineering style in conflict resolution. Furthermore, there may be various reasons why this technique of dispute resolution is not

used. According to Somech (2008), dominating the pattern of managing team issues may be a negative kind of resolution, causing team functioning and performance to suffer. The result is in contrast with the responses of the principals when their responses under Competing got the lowest overall mean of 1.73 and the interpretation of "Seldom". This also suggests that, from the principal's point of view, Competing is their least used style. This further implies that there is a difference in the perception of the teacher-respondents and the principals regarding the principal's use of Competing Style when managing conflict.

Avoiding got the lowest mean of 2.53 and the interpretation of "Often". Though ranked 5th, it was still used by principals often. However, on the responses of the principals, Avoiding got an overall mean of 2.00 and the interpretation of "Seldom". There are various reasons why the avoidance method of conflict resolution is used. Avoidance is essentially a static attitude to conflict, according to Handling Conflict (n.d.); it does nothing to fix problems or make changes that could prevent disputes. However, there are other occasions where avoidance may be beneficial, such as when an issue is of minor importance or when the potential damage from conflict is too significant. Avoidance can also serve as a cooling-off phase, allowing participants to decide how to best resolve the disagreement afterwards.

Generally, the teacher-respondents assessed that the principals used the different conflict management styles "Often" with an overall mean of 2.82. Further, the result implies that, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, the principals frequently involve and assist with teachers in resolving issues in their schools.

Table 3
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Age.

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept Ho
Collaborating	Between Groups	1.29	3	0.43	53.71	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.19	24	0.01			
	Total	1.48	27				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.52	3	0.17	26.58	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.13	20	0.01			
	Total	0.65	23				
Competing	Between Groups	0.95	3	0.32	1.11	<0.05	Accept
	Within Groups	4.55	16	0.28			
	Total	5.50	19				
Avoiding	Between Groups	5.55	3	0.18	5.76	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.64	20	0.03			
	Total	1.19	23				
Compromising	Between Groups	0.20	3	0.07	2.85	<0.05	Accept
	Within Groups	0.27	12	0.02			
	Total	0.47	15				

Table 3 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to age.

Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Competing Style ($F(3,16)=1.11 < cv=3.24$); and, Compromising Style ($F(3,12) < cv=3.49$) when grouped according to age. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that, regardless of age, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principal's use of the Competing and Compromising Style of conflict management.

On the other hand, data also reveal that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(3,24)=53.71 > cv=3.01$); Accommodating Style ($F(3,20)=26.58 > cv=3.10$); and Avoiding Style ($F(3,20)=5.76 > cv=3.10$) when grouped according to age. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, and Avoiding styles vary when grouped according to age. This further means that the principals used collaborating, accommodating and avoiding styles on different levels when managing conflicts of the different age groups.

Table 4
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept Ho
Collaborating	Between Groups	0.22	3	0.07	5.40	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.33	24	0.01			
	Total	0.55	27				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.83	3	0.28	15.57	>0.05	Reject

	Within Groups	0.36	20	0.02			
	Total	1.19	23				
Competing	Between Groups	2.89	3	0.96	4.55	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	3.38	16	0.21			
	Total	6.27	19				
Avoiding	Between Groups	0.79	3	0.26	4.65	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.13	20	0.06			
	Total	1.92	23				
Compromising	Between Groups	0.11	3	0.04	0.49	<0.05	Accept
	Within Groups	0.87	12	0.07			
	Total	0.98	15				

Table 4 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Compromising Style ($F(3,12)=0.49 < cv=3.49$) when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that, regardless of the highest educational attainment, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principal's use of the Compromising Style of conflict management.

Data also reveal that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(3,34)=5.40 > cv=3.01$); Accommodating Style ($F(3,20)=15.57 > cv=3.10$); Competing Style ($F(3,16)=4.55 > cv=3.24$); and, Avoiding Style ($F(3,20)=4.65 > cv=3.10$) when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, and Avoiding styles vary when grouped according to the highest educational attainment.

Table 5

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Length of Service in the School

Area	Source	SS	Df	MS	F	p	Reject / Accept Ho
Collaborating	Between Groups	2.06	4	0.52	35.46	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.45	31	0.01			
	Total	2.51	35				
Accommodating	Between Groups	0.77	4	0.19	22.34	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.22	26	0.01			
	Total	0.99	30				
Competing	Between Groups	1.86	4	0.47	11.28	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.87	21	0.04			
	Total	2.73	25				
Avoiding	Between Groups	1.15	4	0.29	6.76	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	1.11	26	0.04			
	Total	2.26	30				
Compromising	Between Groups	1.27	4	0.32	12.02	>0.05	Reject
	Within Groups	0.42	16	0.03			
	Total	1.69	20				

Table 5 shows the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to the length of service.

Results show that there are significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating Style ($F(4,31)=35.46 > cv=2.69$); Accommodating Style ($F(4,26)=22.34 > cv=2.74$); Competing Style ($F(4,21)=11.28 > cv=2.84$); Avoiding Style ($F(4,26)=6.76 > cv=2.74$); and Compromising Style ($F(4,16)=12.02 > cv=3.00$) when grouped according to the length of service. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, Avoiding, and Compromising styles vary when grouped according to the length of service.

Table 6
Independent Samples Test on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Conflict Management Styles Used by the Principals when Grouped According to Workload

Area	Mean	SS	t	df	cv	Reject / Accept Ho
Collaborating			0.06	12	0.695	Accept
without admin work	3.12	0.01				
with admin work	2.10	0.05				
Accommodating			0.22	10	0.700	Accept
without admin work	2.96	0.02				
with admin work	2.91	0.06				
Competing			0.07	8	0.706	Accept
without admin work	2.62	0.05				
with admin work	2.61	0.14				
Avoiding		-0.42	10	0.700	Accept	
without admin work	2.51	0.07				
with admin work	2.61	0.15				
Compromising			0.26	6	0.718	Accept
without admin work	2.89	0.03				
with admin work	2.83	0.06				

Shown in Table 6 is the result of the Independent Sample test (Independent t-test) which measured if there are significant differences in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the conflict management styles used by the principals when grouped according to workload.

Results show that there are no significant differences on the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of Collaborating ($t=0.06 < cv=0.695$); Accommodating ($t=0.22 < cv=0.700$); Competing ($t=0.07 < cv=0.706$); Avoiding ($t=-0.42 < cv=0.700$); Compromising ($t=0.26 < cv=0.718$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the Collaborating, Accommodating, Competing, Avoiding, and Compromising style of conflict management. Ladeño (as cited by Manila, 2016) found out in his study that majority of the administrators considered integrating as one of the most extreme and highly desirable styles in conflict management. Furthermore, the result agrees with the answers of the principals. Moreover, based on the result, from the teacher-respondents' point of view, the principals often involve and collaborate with the teachers with or without an administrative load in handling conflicts in their schools.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

Though most of the teacher-respondents belong to early adulthood, college graduate; and, have only rendered 5 years and below in the institution, the teacher-respondents still have the maturity to provide a credible assessment on how administrators manage conflicts in their respective schools. Also, almost half of them have rendered more than 6 or more years in the institution, have gained ample experience, and have gone through various working environments that can enable them to give a good gauge on how school administrators manage conflict in their schools.

The teacher-respondents have identified the individual causes of conflicts to be the most common conflicts they experienced in the school. Likewise, the principals have identified "Conflicts in decision making, and different objectives", "Different point of views. Miscommunication", and "Different age gaps or generation, and perceptions" to be the most common conflicts they experience in school. Moreover, the principals use Collaborating Style when dealing with individual causes of conflicts.

Regardless of age, educational attainment, or workload, the teacher-respondents' assessment on the principal's conflict resolution strategies showed that the principals often used the different styles with Collaborating as the most used conflict management style. Results of the study further showed that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on the principals' use of the Competing and Compromising style when grouped according to age. Also, irrespective of workload, the teacher-respondents have the same assessment on the principals' use of the different conflict management styles. However, the responses of the teacher-respondents on the principal's use of conflict resolution strategies vary when grouped according to educational attainment and length of service.

A series of training on the use of conflict management styles and the continuation of professional advancement are needed for principals to be adept at the different conflict management styles and to develop relevant skills in conflict management to manage conflicts at different levels of situations.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby

presented. First, teachers are encouraged to continue their graduate studies in order to update their intellectual qualities. This is one way to address differences in previous experience and knowledge referring to a subject or different perception of the same issue. Further, this could also give them a more comprehensive view or perceptions of the different conflict management and conflict management styles.

It can be also noted that about 40% of the teachers were well-experienced in their teaching career. Considering the above statistics, it is implied that some of the teacher-respondents have somehow gained ample experience and have gone through various conditions and working environments that can able them to give a good gauge on how school administrators manage conflicts in the workplace. Also, they have already gone through situations examining the competence of school managers in handling conflicts.

The principals, based on the result that the individual causes of conflict are high, must investigate the factors that cause conflicts between teacher-teacher or principal-teacher like different previous experiences and knowledge referring to a subject; different perceptions on the same issue; and different objectives, motivations, or interests. This would assist them in determining the true problems and better imagining viable remedies.

The principals, based on the results that the managerial causes of conflict is high, must allocate tasks equally; avoid subjective performance appraisal; and, must establish clear and formal procedures, transparency, efficiency, clarity, and addressability to alleviate or prevent conflicts to worsen. The result agrees with Fisher (as cited by Crossfield and Bourne, 2018) who stated that individuals and groups possess insuppressible needs 35 for identity, dignity, equity, and participation in decisions that affect them. Lack of such fundamental needs in the organization can give rise to conflicts in schools.

Given that the majority of the teacher-respondents were in their early adulthood, implying that they are mature and responsible enough, it is suggested that principals consider the use of conflict management styles with high concern for others, particularly collaborating and accommodating, when dealing with disagreement with their teachers of this age.

Since the school offers scholarships for everyone who wants to continue their professional education, the principals, who are also Masters of Education Major in Educational Management graduates and students, are encouraged to continue their Doctoral Studies so they could gain more knowledge on their field especially on improving their conflict management skills.

The school should implement or conduct a series of training for the principals to be adept at the different conflict management styles; to enhance appropriate skills to manage conflicts at a different level or situation with a view of carrying out the school's vision, mission, goals, and objectives; and, to guide how their junior administrators should manage conflicts, especially in their respective schools.

References

- Amorado, R. V., Boholano, H. B., & Talili, I. N. (2017). *Quantitative research: A practical approach*. Malabon: Mutya Publishing House, Inc.
- Cerado, E. C. (2013). Administrators' conflict resolution strategies and school development in region XII. *National Research Conference*.
- Edet, A., Benson, U., & Williams, R. (2017). Principals' conflict resolution strategies and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 7, 153-154. doi:10.5901/jesr.2017.v7n2p153
- Eklund, A. (2010, August 8). Managing Conflict. Retrieved from <http://andyeklund.com/managing-conflict/>
- Kassim, M., Manaf, A., Abdullah, M., Osman, A., & Salahudin, S. (2018, November). Conflict management styles and job satisfaction: A study among Malaysian Public Universities' Academicians. *Asian journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 7(4), 12-13.
- Manila, B. M. (2016, March). Principals' conflict management styles and their schools' performance among public elementary schools in the district of Mariveles, Bataan. *Academia*, 5-6. Retrieved from http://www.academia.edu/32994842/PRINCIPALS_CONFLICT_MANAGEMENT_STYLES_AND_THEIR_SCHOOLS_PERFORMANCE_AMONG_PUBLIC_ELEMENTARY_SCHOOLS_IN_THE_DISTRICT_OF_MARIVELES_BATAAN
- McNamara, C. (2013). Basics of conflict management: Adapted from the field guide to leadership and supervision. Retrieved January 15, 2020, from <http://managementhelp.org/intrpsnl/basics.htm>
- Msila, V. (2012, July 01). Conflict management and school leadership. *Journal of Communication*, 3, 25-34. doi:10.1080/0976691X.2012.11884792
- Rahim, M. A. (2010). *Managing conflict in organizations* (4th ed.). New York: Transaction Publishers.
- Resources, T. U. (2019, July 29). Resolving conflicts at work: Employee information. Oklahoma City. Retrieved from <https://hr.ou.edu/Employees/Career-Development/Resolving-Conflicts-at-Work>
- Robbins, S. P., Judge, T. A., & Campbell, T. C. (2010). *Organizational behaviour*. Retrieved from Pearson UK: http://wps.pearsoned.co.uk/ema_uk_he_robbins_orgbeuro_1/151/38823/9938864
- Sumera-Icutan, S., & Sumera-Sagaoinit, C. (2017). Conflicts and resolutions of the school administrators: Basis for innovative administrative program. *Asia Pacific Journal of Contemporary Education and Communication Technology*, 3(1), 252-253.

- Thomas, K. W., & Killmann, R. H. (2015). An overview of the Thomas-Kilman conflict mode instrument (TKI). *Kilman Diagnostics*. Retrieved January 10, 2020, from <http://www.kilmandiagnostics.com/overview-thomas-kilman-conflict-mode-instrument-tki>
- Uchendu, C. C., Anijaobi-idem, F. N., & Odigwe, F. N. (2013). Conflict management and organizational performance in secondary schools on Cross River State, Nigeria. *Research Journal in Organizational Psychology and Educational Studies*, 2(2), 66-71. Retrieved January 14, 2020, from <http://www.emergingresource.org>